

INTELLECTUAL-PEDAGOGICAL STRUCTURE OF DEVELOPING ANALYTICAL THINKING IN FUTURE PEDAGOGUES

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Abstract: In the article, the intellectual-pedagogical structure of developing analytical thinking in future pedagogues, methods and stages of its organization are studied and analyzed.

Key words: analytical thinking, structural structure, logical, critical and analytical thinking, improvement, pedagogue, intellectual-pedagogical structure.

INTRODUCTION. Today, unlike in the past, educating a new generation of independent thinking and creative pedagogues remains one of our main problems. "Indeed, during the student years, young people rise to the stage of biological maturity, and from a social point of view, maturity and physical maturity. In students, important aspects of intelligence, such as self-control, self-evaluation, self-awareness, and self-management, will rise to a new high level of development. General professional, socio-humanitarian and specialized sciences play an important role in the development of students' thinking and the formation of a scientific worldview" [1].

Such qualities, skills and abilities that develop analytical thinking are very important for the future pedagogue to become a competitive specialist. Strong leaders cannot be developed without these skills and abilities. Such qualities are also highly valued by employers of powerful countries. Taking into account the increasing importance of these qualities today, it becomes clear how analytical thinking can be useful for future pedagogues.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. Analytical thinking has been researched by many scientists in various disciplines, especially philosophy, psychology, and pedagogy, and this process continues today. Among them, D. Sharipova, O. Musurmonova, M. Kuronov, U. Mahkamov, R. Safarova, Sh. Mardonov, D. Roziyeva, N. Egamberdiyeva, Sh. Shodmonova, Sh. Sharipov, O. Jamoldinova, V. Slastenin, I. Isayev, Y. Shiyanov, Z. T. Soliyeva's scientific research studies have explored the philosophical, psychological and pedagogical aspects of analytical thinking, existing problems and the factors to overcome them.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. Thinking is formed directly depending on the age characteristics of a person. According to the results of psychological-pedagogical research, the content and structure of thinking is gradually formed and developed. An intellectual creative process is noted as a high level of

thinking. The quality and efficiency of this process is related to the quality of education and training. That is why it is necessary to pay special attention to the development of analytical thinking in future pedagogues.

A person not only perceives the environment, but also wants to understand it. Understanding means getting into the essence of things and events, being able to distinguish the most important thing in them. "In this sense, among the factors that shape thinking, the competence of observation, perception, analysis, evaluation of the environment and the ability to express a personal reaction to them is recognized as a structural component that enriches the content of thinking" [3].

The great German philosopher I. Kant observed the essence of the world and believed that it can never be known. The main source of knowledge is our emotions, which give us certain ideas about the world. As a result of the development of science and practice, it was found that these views are incorrect. Most philosophers are convinced that we have the ability to know the world, that our ideas and theories describe things approximately as they exist, that is, they contain reality. Analytical thinking is aimed at understanding events both in terms of content and form and, of course, in essence.

The driving force of the thinking process consists of contradictions between the goal and the means at the disposal of the subject. Despite the fact that thought processes are always unique, it is possible to highlight common features in them. This factor is evident in the stages of solving problem situations. A problematic situation always appears as an obstacle, a gap in activity. Steps to resolve a problem situation are as follows:

- to be aware of the problematic situation;
- identifying known and unknown things (as a result, the problem becomes a task);
- limiting the search space based on the type of task, structures, and ideas about experience appropriate to the task;
- emergence of a hypothesis;
- hypothesis testing.

Although thinking as a process of generalized and indirect knowledge of the structural elements of analytical thinking always includes elements of productivity, the ratio may be different in the process of mental activity. The novelty of the problem determines the unique way to solve it. In this process, intuitive-practical generalizations are very important, along with verbal-logical, well-learned generalizations. They appear in the process of analyzing visual

situations, solving specific practical problems, real actions with objects or their models, which makes it very easy to search for unknown things, but this search process is intuitively outside the field of consciousness.

In order to develop the analytical thinking of future pedagogues, first of all, it is necessary to be aware of the techniques and rules of self-organization, mental activity. A student should understand the essence of mental work with sufficient accuracy, at least be aware of its main methods. If he does not have the desire and ability to organize his mental activity, he usually cannot achieve a high level of development of thinking even with the most favorable inclinations and good conditions. To increase the efficiency of mental activity, it is possible to use the advantages of the concept, the ability to control the stages of thinking, such as setting a task, creating optimal motivation, organizing the direction of associations, and maximally including both figurative and symbolic components. Thinking, as well as reducing unnecessary criticality in evaluating the result - all this allows you to activate the thinking process, make it more effective. After all, it is necessary to create such a mechanism for the development of analytical thinking. The ability to logically process material often develops spontaneously in adolescents. Development of such skills should be a special task of the future pedagogue.

For the correct development of thinking, the future teacher uses every opportunity - to analyze, compare and contrast things and events, to teach them to clearly and correctly express their thoughts, to reason, to draw conclusions. and generalization.

Its functional components, like the components of the overall pedagogical system, have their own specific technologies. Solving important issues of the educational process on the basis of a technological approach to the problem, following the knowledge of specific parts and stages of the pedagogical system, developing the analytical thinking of future pedagogues in the pedagogical process and strengthening it, gradually achieving this goal, thus the future all-round development of the teacher, readiness to form a well-rounded person is ensured. For this purpose, regular pedagogical influence on students is planned. The most important thing in the pedagogical process is the readiness of future pedagogues to develop analytical thinking. For this, it is necessary to ensure the proportionality of the purpose, content, forms and methods of this process. Their compatibility with the process of development of analytical thinking is manifested in the technological system.

Attention is paid to the structure, systematicity, stages, principles, main parts of pedagogical technologies, covering the content of specific educational science and lectures. The post-lecture parts of the educational process focus on strengthening the knowledge of future pedagogues on the development of analytical thinking, repeating its main parts, and completing the educational process organized on the basis of the lecture.

During the course of the research, during the lectures aimed at developing the analytical thinking of the future pedagogues, attention was paid to the following: determining the purpose of the educational process; creating an inclination towards the educational process; "activating students' attention and perception; increase the participation of students in the lecture process; to repeat and reinforce the new educational materials presented to students, to conclude the lectures; giving assignments to students on the subject; such as recommending the necessary literature and additional sources for lecture materials" [2].

It is worth noting that the technology of the specific educational unit, lecturing, taking into account learning inclinations, goal orientation, explaining the content of the educational material, clarifying the content of the lectures to the students with the help of tables and schemes It consists of such parts as delivering, summarizing and strengthening the learned topic, concluding the lesson, giving recommendations to students, giving assignments, describing students' educational activities and the educational process, and giving an assessment. As a result of modifying the technology of this educational unit, effective results were achieved in the development of analytical thinking of future pedagogues. For example, in the development of analytical thinking: social, personal and professional inclinations of future pedagogues to develop analytical thinking were strengthened; The importance of using advanced teaching methods in the development of analytical thinking, and for this, being able to master and analyze them in depth, was emphasized, and guaranteed results were obtained in this field. By setting a goal for the educational process, the students' interest in learning the possibilities of interdisciplinary cooperation was strengthened, the content of the knowledge they need to acquire, and the interesting and complex aspects of the future pedagogue's activity were revealed. Based on this, the expected results and professional goals of the future pedagogue were defined. Thus, by setting the goals of the process of developing the analytical thinking of future pedagogues, the possibilities of achieving the intended result were revealed.

Summarization of lecture materials is carried out by both teachers and students. The post-lecture parts of the educational process also have a certain didactic structure. These parts include strengthening the subject, using multiple-choice questions, and independently completing the lecture by the teacher or students. As a pedagogical result of such training, recommendations are drawn up on the use of the selected educational material in pedagogical practice. The main part of these recommendations is offered by teachers, and students make additions to these recommendations, activating their pedagogical and creative imagination. Reinforcement-repetition moments after the lecture include the following parts: conducting questions and answers, completing test tasks, students reading their written lectures, etc.

In order to develop the analytical thinking of future pedagogues, lectures should be based on certain requirements: the following should be recognized as their main ones: students' feelings, experiences; taking into account the goals and inclinations set for themselves; ensuring the comprehensibility, consistency, wealth of evidence, and reliability of the lecture text; to achieve quick understanding of the lecture text by students; achieving diversity and multivariate forms, methods, methods and means of presenting lectures to students; be able to effectively use visual aids during lectures; encourage students to independent thinking, creativity, and deep reflection during lectures; perception of future teachers; such as revealing the possibilities of using the knowledge of future pedagogues regarding the development of analytical thinking in practice [4,5].

CONCLUSION. Narrative and narration methods are widely used in the presentation of lecture materials aimed at developing the analytical thinking of future pedagogues. For this, it is recommended to use bright, meaningful, memorable visual aids. During the lecture, it is of particular pedagogical importance to search for a solution to the problem posed by questions inviting students to debate, to ensure that students are ready to debate, to enrich their interest in works of visual art, and to form new interests in this field in them. . After all, during the lecture, the teacher should be equally attentive to all students.

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